

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PERSONALITY

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Abstract. *This article provides definitions of the socio-psychological characteristics of personality and the scientific analysis of scientists on the structure of personality, as well as views on the role of personality in social life. Today, in the field of psychology, the problematic issues of personality structure and its components are of great relevance. A number of studies are being conducted in the field of psychology to explore this issue.*

Keywords: *static structure, universal psychological characteristics, socially specific features, individual and unique qualities, internal system, national, professional, economic, political, class unity, psychological image, socially conditioned orientation, substructure, dynamic structure.*

Introduction. In studying the socio-psychological characteristics of personality, it is necessary to take into account the opinions and scientific views of both foreign scholars and those from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS).

A personality is an individual who is the product of social and interpersonal relations and the subject of conscious activity. The most important characteristic of personality is its direct connection with complex social relations and its dual role as both the object and the subject of social activity. One of the most essential qualities of personality is that it perceives and internalizes external social influences through its consciousness and cognition (as an object) and then acts upon them (as a subject). It is well known that the issue of personality is studied in general psychology, developmental and educational psychology, differential psychology, legal psychology, and a number of other specialized branches. Each branch examines personality issues according to its own subject and objectives. For instance, general psychology considers personality as a product of psychological activity and the bearer of individual mental processes, while sociology views it as an object of social relations.

Main Part. The distinct feature of the socio-psychological approach to personality lies in its interpretation of personality as the result of various forms of interaction with different groups. In other words, social psychology primarily studies the laws governing the behavior of an individual as a member of a group and how social interactions are reflected in the individual's consciousness. According to B.D. Parigin, the static structure of personality includes the following:

1. Universal psychological characteristics;
2. Socially specific features related to nationality, profession, economy, politics, and class unity;
3. Individual and unique personal traits.

In our opinion, each of these characteristics exists within the human psyche; they do not represent separate or isolated sets of traits but rather form an integrated system. According to the

American psychologist G. Allport, personality is an “internal system,” a “dynamic organization,” a “self,” or a kind of “metapsychological self” that embodies pre-determined goals and dispositions, harmoniously shaping human thought and behavior. For this reason, the class-historical assessment of personality often remains underexplored, and psychological interpretation takes the place of social analysis.

As B.D. Parigin strongly asserts, the leading feature of the dynamic structure of personality is its close relation to time and its dependence on the state of the psyche or the activity of the individual. Parigin identifies two main aspects of this structure — mental states and behavior. In his view, a person’s mood or psychological readiness plays a crucial role, serving as an indicator of renewal and transformation within the personality.

The dynamic functional structure of personality proposed by K.K. Platonov arouses great scientific interest. The scholar strives to create a multi-level model that encompasses the full diversity of personality traits. According to Platonov, the elements of personality structure are its properties, characteristics, and image. He distinguishes four interrelated substructures of personality, each reflecting different aspects of the individual.

1. The socially conditioned substructure, which unites a person’s moral image, attitudes, and orientation. The traits related to this substructure are not directly connected with natural inclinations and are formed through education and upbringing.
2. The substructure of experience, which includes knowledge, skills, habits, and competencies acquired through learning. However, as Platonov emphasizes, this process occurs under the influence of the biologically conditioned traits of an individual. Through this substructure, a person assimilates the historical experience of humankind.
3. The substructure of individual characteristics, which determines certain psychological processes such as types of memory, stability of emotional reactions, and modes of learning. Here, the influence of biologically conditioned characteristics is even more evident.
4. The biologically conditioned substructure, which combines biopsychic features, temperament (typological traits), gender and age characteristics, and also includes possible pathological changes in the individual. This substructure develops through training and depends on the morphological and physiological characteristics of the brain. According to Platonov, this substructure forms the foundation of the personality’s image and essential traits.

The psychologist V.S. Merlin also paid special attention to the structure of personality. He believed that one of its essential components, which cannot be divided into smaller parts, is a person’s traits. Each trait reflects a specific direction or orientation and embodies the individual’s attitudes. Based on this, Merlin defined the structure of personality as a “symptom complex” — an organized and interrelated system of personality traits that express a person’s attitude toward themselves, others, and labor.

Unlike other theorists, R. Cattell did not immerse himself in excessive observation or rely solely on intuitive understanding of human nature. Instead, his approach was based on precise empirical methods and observation. The structure of Cattell’s scientific model is guided by a single leading goal: to identify the fundamental traits of personality using the method of factor analysis. Similar to Allport, Cattell believed that personality traits form core structures responsible for human behavior. However, unlike Allport, he rejected the notion that traits exist only within a person’s internal world. In his view, traits have no concrete neurophysiological status, yet they can be observed through behavioral patterns.

Cattell's objective and statistically grounded analysis of behavioral characteristics deserves recognition. His theory represents a comprehensive and well-developed framework in modern psychology. Despite its complexity, it remains a crucial concept for anyone aiming to study personality systematically. Cattell's theory attempts to explain the complex interrelation between the personality system and the socio-cultural matrix in which it functions. He emphasizes that any adequate model of personality must take into account the set of traits, personality-forming factors, genetic peculiarities, the influence of environment, and the interaction between heredity and environment — all of which affect human behavior. According to Cattell, the theory of proper functioning and development of personality must rely on rigorous research methods and precise measurements.

Conclusion. In conclusion, when studying the socio-psychological characteristics of a person, analyzing the opinions of various scholars shows that B. D. Parigin emphasized the universal psychological traits inherent in a person, as well as the social characteristics related to national, professional, economic, political, and class affiliations, along with the individual and unique qualities of the personality. According to the American psychologist G. Allport, a person is an “inner system,” a “dynamic structure,” a “self,” or a “metapsychological self” that reflects predetermined goals and dispositions, shaping human thought and behavior in harmony. K. K. Platonov's theory of the structure of personality also arouses great interest. Thus, to comprehensively resolve the issue of the structure of personality, it is necessary to adhere to certain essential conditions.

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